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Viremic non-progression in HIV-1.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We demonstrate here that viremic non-progressors express high levels of the IL-23 cytokine subunit //23a. Viral progression can be thought to be a function of or influenced by IL-23 signaling.

Citations

1. Hunter, C.A., 2005. New IL-12-family members: IL-23 and IL-27, cytokines with divergent functions. *Nature Reviews Immunology*, 5(7), pp.521-531.

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